

THE IMPACT OF LEVERAGING ENGLISH PROFICIENCY IN ENHANCING THE TOURISM SECTOR IN EL OUED*

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Abstract

The current study aims at investigating the relationship between foreign languages and tourism emphasizing the effect of English language proficiency on the tourism sector. The study uses a quantitative descriptive design to collect the data through a structured questionnaire designed for tourism agencies' staff and tour guides in the province of El OUED. Additionally, it depends on reviewing previous studies on English for Tourism and tourism sectors in Algeria. The findings of the study reveal that English proficiency significantly influence southern Algeria's tourism sector by empowering communication for tourism employees, developing customer service, and gaining economic opportunities. Hence, mastering English plays an important role in promoting the tourism industry as a whole. The results focus on the urgent need to improve English language skills and promote positive communication between tourists and locals. It is also recommended incorporating English language proficiency within academic curricula through partnership with educational institutions.

Key words: *Tourism sector, English proficiency, Tourism agencies' staff, Tour guides.*

1. Introduction

English is a global language due to its widespread use and influence in international communication, business, science, and technology (Hoa, 2023). It is an essential tool for global communication because millions of people around the world speak English as a first or second language (Rao, 2019). Tourism has become a fundamental and leading sector in economic and social development. Algeria is famous for its different natural and cultural resources, which attract visitors from the world. Thus, the ability to communicate effectively in English enrich experience for

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all involved. In fact, native and non-native speakers can connect via English language because it facilitates communication and reduces misunderstandings. Many studies have focused on the importance of the English language in the tourism sector. According to AL-Ragdhi and Al-Arashi (2024), in Indonesia Widiastuti (2021) studied the role of English in developing tourism, in Albania, Gjata (2017) studied the English and its role in the development of tourism in Albania and in the world. In Croatia, Bobanovic (2011) studied the importance of English language skills in the tourism sector. However, no study has been conducted on the importance of the English language for tourism in EI OUED yet. Therefore, this study aims at exploring the importance of English proficiency, the benefits it can bring to tourism sector in EI OUED. The following main question and sub-questions are formulated to achieve this aim:

To what extent does leveraging English proficiency contribute to enhance the tourism sector in EI OUED province?

1. Does English proficiency have an effect on facilitating the communication between tourist and locals in EI OUED?
2. Does English proficiency have an effect on developing customer service and satisfaction?
3. Does English proficiency have an effect in gaining economic opportunities for tourist guides in EI OUED?
4. Are there differences between the average responses of the sample due to the respondent's personal information (gender, age, educational level, experience, type of agency)?

The hypotheses of the study are formulated as follows:

1. There is a significant positive impact of leveraging English proficiency in facilitating the communication between tourist and locals in EI OUED.
2. There is a significant positive impact of leveraging English proficiency in developing customer service and satisfaction.
3. There is a positive impact of leveraging English proficiency in gaining economic opportunities for tourist guides in EI OUED.
4. There are no statistically significant differences between the average responses of the participants due to their demographic variables (gender, age, educational level, experience, and type of agency).

2. English language proficiency

English proficiency is the ability to use English language effectively in a real-life situation by focusing on its four skills: listening, speaking, reading and writing. That is, proficiency contains the ability to listen, understand and communicate effectively in the target situations, and more importantly, the ability to decode words in order to understand the pragmatic meaning (SCERT, Bihar, 2011). There are many standardized tests to measure English proficiency such as IELTS, TOEFL, Duolingo English Test, or Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR) with six levels: A1, A2, B1, B2, C1, C2 (Tang & Nguyen, 2025). According to Renandya et al. (2004), indicators have presented five performances to assess learners' language proficiency as key issues in six levels, including accuracy, fluency, complexity,

appropriacy and capacity, and the three extended categories: Basic users A1, A2; Intermediate user B1, B2 and Proficient users C1, C2. Therefore, the framework provides detailed information on what people can do with using the language appropriately, fluently or accurately using (as cited in Tang & Nguyen, 2025).

3. Tourism in Algeria

Nowadays, Tourism has become a fundamental and leading sector in economic and social development. Tourists move from one destination to another due to various reasons such as pleasure, business, discovery and many other reasons; thus, they can contribute effectively to economic and social development. Algeria is a competitive destination due to its different natural and cultural resources; however, the existence of certain obstacles impedes this sector and make it more vulnerable.

Algeria is the largest country in Africa. It offers a variety of tourist attractions, including its historical past, its climate and its geography particularly Sahara. The latter is the second largest Sahara in the world due to its area nearing two million km² and covering nearly 80 % of the country's area. Algeria has been a member of the World Tourism Organization since 1976. The Sahara is one of the main tourist attractions due to its natural and cultural heritage such as Ghardaïa, Hoggar, and Tassili. These places and others contribute to Algerian international market and tourism industry (Boumelit, 2023). Thus, the government interests in developing the country's travel and tourism industry, with emphasis on Saharan and its cultural tourism.

Since 2005, Algeria has reformed its legislation to ease foreign and local investments in the tourism (Zeghouani & Maouche, 2021). Although the number of international tourists in Algeria increased from 2015 forward accounting two millions in 2019, it declined sharply in 2020; then, after the 2020 tourism crisis driven by the COVID-19 pandemic, the tourism industry slowly recovered accounting for around 04% percent of the country's GDP (Statista Research Department, 2024). Then, according to the Travel and Tourism Competitiveness Report 2024, the Algerian tourism industry improved in 2024 compared to 2017 and 2019. Since then, Algeria has advanced across all indicators, including safety and security, health and hygiene, human resources and labor market, ICT readiness, and land and sea transport infrastructure. However, challenges remain such as limited progress in international openness, declines in environmental sustainability and tourism service infrastructure (Benramdane & Boumediene, 2025).

In conclusion, the tourism sector has an important role in the development of the economy. Algeria, like other countries in the world, is rich in important tourist capacities based on its natural and historical attractions. However, the country's tourism sector has faced different challenges especially the coronavirus, which led to a global crisis in the travel industry and affected Algeria. Then, the tourism grew slowly. Finally, the government is working to advance its tourism sector and develop it again.

4. Methodology

4.1. Participants

In order to evaluate the impact of English proficiency on tourism sector in El OUED, this study implemented a quantitative design. Agencies' staff were selected

from different agencies to ensure sample diversity. They are from different agencies such as BEN ALI Tourism and Travel, BOURAS Travel, wherever Travel and Sotrav Travel. The research was conducted during December 2025 at El OUED.

Twenty-five questionnaires were distributed to the study sample. Out of these, twenty-two questionnaires were returned, representing a high response rate. After reviewing the returned forms, two questionnaires were excluded for being invalid or incomplete. Therefore, the final number used for statistical analysis was twenty.

Regarding the sample size (Twenty agencies' staff), it is essential to note that research in English for Specific Purposes (ESP) often deals with small, highly specialized professional groups rather than the general public. As argued by ESP scholars, the focus in such studies is on 'depth rather than breadth,' aiming to capture the specific linguistic needs and challenges within a particular workplace context (EL OUED). Given that the total number of active travel agencies in this region is limited, a sample of twenty participants represents a significant and representative proportion of the actual professional community. Hence, while the sample size may limit broad generalization, it provides high-quality, context-specific insights that are fundamental to ESP curriculum design and needs analysis.

4.2. Instruments

The study explores the importance of English proficiency, the benefits it can bring to tourism sector in El OUED. Therefore, it conducts quantitative questionnaire items to ensure collecting responses from the participants of the analysis and the accuracy of the results. In addition to the personal information, the questionnaire was divided into three parts to collect responses related to the research questions of the study.

To test the research hypotheses, the collected data were analysed using SPSS. Statistical significance was determined at the level of 0.05 level. Therefore, if the value is less than or equal to 5 %, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating a statistically significant difference. Conversely, if the value exceeds 5 %, the null hypothesis is retained.

The questionnaire was presented to some specialists in the field to ensure its validity allowing for the effective and reliable collection of data. The questionnaire was also checked for reliability using Cronbach Alpha, Table 1.

Table 1. Reliability statistics

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the outputs of SPSS 26

Statements	Cronbach's Alpha		
	Cronbach's Alpha coefficient	Items	Result
Number of Items part 02	0.664	05	reliable
Number of Items part 03	0.809	05	reliable
Number of Items part 04	0.771	05	reliable
Total	0.906	15	reliable

5. Results and discussion

There are three independent variables. The hypothesis of a difference between the mean of the sample's responses is tested based on the personal variables and the one-sign test. The latter is a non-parametric test that reveals the orientation of the sample's responses and their perception of the existence of an effect of English language or not on facilitating communication, developing services, or gaining economic opportunities (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. The Study Modal
Source: Prepared by the researcher

5.1. Results of the questionnaire

5.1.1. General information

In this study, diagram1 demonstrates that males are more numerous than females. That is, 75.00 % of tourism employees are Males and 25.00 % are Females (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Diagram of participants' Gender
Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the outputs of SPSS 26

As underscored in Diagram 2, the vast majority of the participants are aged between 30-40 years old, i.e. nine participants from the global number, and only one participant is more than 50 years old (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Diagram of participants' age

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the outputs of SPSS 26

As indicated in Diagram 3, the majority of the sample are university graduates at 60 %, followed by those with a secondary level or less and professionals at 15 %, and finally 10 % for the postgraduate degrees (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. Diagram of participants' qualifications

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the outputs of SPSS 26

As displayed in the below diagram 4, the highest percentage of experience is from 1 to 5 years. That is, nine employees have less than five years of experience, which indicates a lack of experience in the study sample. Then, six employees are experienced from 6 to 10 years. Finally, just two participants are expertise in the tourism sector more than 10 years old (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. Diagram of participants' experiences

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the outputs of SPSS 26

The diagram 5 denotes clearly that 80 % of the study sample are working in travel agencies, while the remaining 20 % are equally divided between private agencies and tour guides.

Figure 6. Diagram of the type of agency

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the outputs of SPSS 26

5.1.2. Results of other parts and testing the Hypotheses

The table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation values of the opinions and trends of the sample members. Consequently, the trends of the sample's responses in all study's parts tend towards agreement and strong agreement as follow: With an average rating of 4.32 out of 5 and a standard deviation of 0.528, tourism employee's consensus solidly supports the notion that proficiency in English is essential for improving the overall experience of tourists in El OUED. Hence, English language plays a significance role in facilitating clear communication, and providing detailed information.

Tourism employees in El OUED held a strong belief in the crucial role of the English language within the tourism industry. With an average rating of 4.22 and a standard deviation of 0.587, they consensus strongly agree the notion that English proficiency is essential in improving customer service and satisfaction.

Table 02 displays that the employees appreciate the significant role of the English language in the tourism industry. With an average rating of 4.17 and a standard deviation of 0.626, it is clear that they place significant an agreement on the ability to speak English fluently when interacting with tourists. Therefore, English proficiency plays a pivotal role in gaining economic opportunities.

Table 2. The general trend of the sample's responses regarding the study's parts

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the outputs of SPSS 26

Statements	Std. Deviation	Mean	Ranking	Direction
English language proficiency improve the overall experience of tourists in El OUED.	.696	4.80	1	Strongly agree
English proficiency protect the natural and cultural heritage in El OUED.	.671	4.35	3	Strongly agree

having employees who are proficient in English has a positive impact on the reputation of the place as a tourist destination	.754	4.40	2	Strongly agree
A lack of English language skills hinders the ability to understand the needs and desires of tourists	1.226	3.85	5	agree
The importance of incorporating English language learning into training programs for tourism sector employees	.523	4.20	4	agree
The contribution of English proficiency in facilitating communication	.528	4.32		Strongly agree
Using English proficiency reduces the frustrations and complaints of foreign tourists.	.768	4.20	3	agree
English proficiency allows tour guides to understand tourist' requests immediately without translation.	.759	4.55	1	Strongly agree
Having employees who are proficient in English has a positive impact on the tourist' satisfaction.	.826	4.05	4	agree
The tourist' satisfaction positively influence their loyalty	.639	4.25	2	Strongly agree
Tourist' satisfaction and their loyalty have direct influence in increasing external marketing.	.887	4.05	5	agree
the role English proficiency in developing customer service and satisfaction	.587	4.22		Strongly agree
Using English language skills has positive impact in promoting EI OUED heritage	1.152	3.80	5	agree
It is important of implementing regular training courses to improve English language skills of employees working in the EI OUED tourism sector.	.865	4.30	2	Strongly agree
Effective communication in English contributes to increasing revenue for the tourism industry of EI OUED.	.671	4.15	3	agree
Developing the level of English language proficiency within the local community will increase employment opportunities in the tourism.	.672	4.15	4	agree
English proficiency gains new economic opportunities for the residents of EI OUED.	.887	4.45	1	Strongly agree
the crucial role of English proficiency in gaining economic opportunities	.626	4.17		agree

5.2. Testing the Hypotheses

Before testing the hypotheses, it must be determine whether the data follows a normal distribution or not through using Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests. By setting the following two hypotheses at a significance level of 0.05, H₀ indicates that the data follows a normal distribution whereas H₁ shows the data does not follow a normal distribution.

As indicated in the table 3. The results of the two tests show that the level of probability values (sig) for all the respondents' data are less than 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, meaning that the results of the Tests of Normality indicate that the data of the sample's responses does not follow a normal distribution. Therefore, non-parametric tests is used to analyze the responses and opinions of the sample members and to test the study hypotheses.

Table 3. Results of (Tests of Normality) for the sample members' responses

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the outputs of SPSS 26

	Kolmogorov-Smirnova			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	Df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
the contribution of English proficiency in facilitating communication	.252	20	.002	.839	20	.004
the role English proficiency in developing customer service and satisfaction	.236	20	.005	.836	20	.003
the crucial role of English proficiency in gaining economic opportunities	.243	20	.003	.784	20	.001

5.2.1. Testing the hypothesis 1

The table below shows that only one participant's response were less than or equal to three, while 19 participants' responses were either agree or strongly agree. Based on the results of the one-sign test, the significance value was (sig = 0.000), which is less than the significance level of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis (H₀) is rejected whereas the alternative hypothesis (H₁) is accepted. To conclude, there is a significant positive impact of leveraging English proficiency on facilitating the communication between tourist and locals in EI OUED at a significant level of 5%.

Table 4. Results of the testing the hypothesis 1

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the outputs of SPSS 26

Binomial Test						
		Category	N	Observed Prop.	Test Prop.	Exact Sig. (2-tailed)
the contribution of English proficiency in facilitating communication	Group 1	<= 3	1	.05	.50	.000
	Group 2	> 3	19	.95		
	Total		20	1.00		

5.2.2. Testing the hypothesis 2

As highlighted in the table 5. Only two participant's responses were less than or equal to three, whereas 18 participant's responses were either agree or strongly agree. Based on the results of the one-sign test, the significance value was (sig = 0.000). Thus, the null hypothesis (H0) is rejected while the alternative hypothesis (H1) is accepted. Consequently, there is a significant positive impact of leveraging English proficiency on developing customer service and satisfaction at a significant level of 5 %.

Table 5. Results of the testing the hypothesis 2

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the outputs of SPSS 26

Binomial Test						
		Category	N	Observed Prop.	Test Prop.	Exact Sig. (2-tailed)
the role English proficiency in developing customer service and satisfaction	Group 1	<= 3	2	.10	.50	.000
	Group 2	> 3	18	.90		
	Total		20	1.00		

5.2.3. Testing the hypothesis 3

The table below displays that only one participant's response were less than or equal to three, while 19 participants' responses were either agree or strongly agree. Based on the results of the one-sign test, the significance value was (sig = 0.000). Hence, the null hypothesis (H0) is rejected while the alternative hypothesis (H1) is accepted. Consequently, there is a positive impact of leveraging English proficiency in gaining economic opportunities for tourist guides in EI OUED at a significant level of 5 %.

Table 6. Results of the testing the hypothesis 3

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the outputs of SPSS 26

Binomial Test						
		Category	N	Observed Prop.	Test Prop.	Exact Sig. (2-tailed)
the crucial role of English proficiency in gaining economic opportunities	Group 1	<= 3	1	.05	.50	.000
	Group 2	> 3	19	.95		
	Total		20	1.00		

5.2.4. Testing the hypothesis 4

To test the difference hypothesis, both Mann-Whitney U and Kruskal-Wallis H tests are used. They are non-parametric tests and are used to determine differences in the average responses of the sample according to the general characteristics of the study sample. In this study, there are five characteristics (gender, age, educational

level, experience, type of agency). Therefore, the main hypothesis followed by five sub-hypotheses as follows:

5.2.4.1. The main hypothesis

There are no statistically significant differences between the average responses of the participants due to their demographic variables (gender, age, educational level, experience, and type of agency).

5.2.4.2. The sub-hypotheses

According to the gender, there are no differences between the average responses of the sample on the study's parts at a significance level of 0.05.

As noted from the results of the table 7. For the Mann-Whitney test, all significance values are greater than 0.05. Thus, the first sub-hypothesis is accepted. i.e., there are no differences between the average responses of the sample on the study's parts due the gender at a significance level of 0.05.

Table 7. Testing the differences between the study's parts

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the outputs of SPSS 26

Test Statistics ^a			
	PART 02	PART 03	PART 04
Mann-Whitney U	22.500	27.000	23.500
Wilcoxon W	37.500	42.000	38.500
Z	-1.330-	-.936-	-1.265-
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.183	.349	.206
Exact Sig. [2*(1-tailed Sig.)]	.197 ^b	.395 ^b	.230 ^b

a. Grouping Variable: Gender
 b. Not corrected for ties.

According to the age, there are no differences between the average responses of the sample on the study's parts at a significance level of 0.05. from the results of the Kruskal-Wallis H test in table below, all significance values are greater than 0.05. Hence, the second sub-hypothesis is accepted. i.e., there are no differences between the average responses of the sample on the study's parts due to the age at a significance level of 0.05.

Table 8. Testing the differences between the study's parts

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the outputs of SPSS 26

Test Statistics ^{a,b}			
	PART 02	PART 03	PART 04
Kruskal-Wallis H	3.726	4.389	6.759
df	3	3	3
Asymp. Sig.	.293	.222	.080

According to the educational level, there are no differences between the average responses of the sample on the study's parts at a significance level of 0.05.

The results of the Kruskal-Wallis H test shows that all significance values are more than 0.05 (table 9). Hence, the third sub-hypothesis is accepted. i.e., there are no differences between the average responses of the sample on the study's parts due to the educational level at a significance level of 0.05.

Table 9. Testing the differences between the study's parts

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the outputs of SPSS 26

Test Statistics ^{a,b}			
	PART 02	PART 03	PART 04
Kruskal-Wallis H	.682	.550	.701
df	3	3	3
Asymp. Sig.	.878	.908	.873

According to the experience, there are no differences between the average responses of the sample on the study's parts at a significance level of 0.05.

The results of the Kruskal-Wallis H test shows that all significance values are more than 0.05 (table 10). Hence, the fourth sub-hypothesis is accepted. i.e., there are no differences between the average responses of the sample on the study's parts due to the experience at a significance level of 0.05.

Table 10. Testing the differences between the study's parts

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the outputs of SPSS 26

Test Statistics ^{a,b}			
	PART 02	PART 03	PART 04
Kruskal-Wallis H	6.314	1.253	5.533
df	3	3	3
Asymp. Sig.	.097	.740	.137

According to type of agency, there are no differences between the average responses of the sample on the study's parts at a significance level of 0.05.

According to The results of the Kruskal-Wallis H test in table above, all significance values are more than 0.05 (table 11). Hence, the fifth sub-hypothesis is accepted. i.e., there are no differences between the average responses of the sample on the study's parts due to the type of agency at a significance level of 0.05.

Table 11. Testing the differences between the study's parts

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the outputs of SPSS 26

Test Statistics ^{a,b}			
	PART 02	PART 03	PART 04
Kruskal-Wallis H	8.335	7.990	4.735
df	2	2	2
Asymp. Sig.	.055	.068	.094

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study has demonstrated that English proficiency is a fundamental pillar for El OUED province to achieve its strategic goal of sustainable tourism development. Through the analysis of the gathered data, the research questions were addressed and the hypotheses were confirmed. These findings align with Al-Ragdhi and Al-Arashi (2024), who highlighted that linguistic competence is a primary driver for tourism in emerging destinations.

Promoting English language serves as a bridge for mutual understanding, which is essential for El OUED proficiency. Culturally, as noted by Crystal (2012), English establishes itself as an international tourist destination. This result is consistent with the "Needs Analysis" conducted by Zeghouani and Maouche (2021) for tourism agencies in El OUED and Jijel.

Based on the proven hypotheses, it is recommended that stakeholders focus on establishing language initiatives adapted for professionals, following the proficiency frameworks suggested by SCERT (2011). To ensure quality instruction, the proficiency of trainers must be prioritized, a factor underscored by Richards and Rodgers (2014) in their pedagogical frameworks. Finally, the study emphasizes addressing language barriers to overcome structural constraints previously identified by Boumelit (2023).

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